

Dynamics of the Acrobot

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Technical Report AIR-25-13

Abstract

The acrobot is a well-known nonlinear dynamical system frequently used as a benchmark in control theory. It has been studied in depth in both simulation and real mechanisms. This report shows how to apply conventional methods to derive its equations of motion.

Keywords: Dynamical systems; Nonlinear dynamics; Equations of motion; Acrobot system.

1 Introduction

The acrobot is a planar two-link underactuated robot like a gymnast on a parallel bar, with one only actuator in the second joint (Fig. 1). The first joint is underactuated, so the motion is made by the actuator and the inertia. The most common problem is the swing-up, in which the robot end must go up to a predefined height, usually above the parallel bar. The balance problem in the upper unstable position is also frequently studied.

Figure 1: Schematic of the acrobot, where l_1 and l_2 are lengths of links, θ_1 and θ_2 are the angles of the first and second joints, respectively, and τ is the torque applied at the second joint. Although they are not represented in the figure other parameters used are the masses of links m_1 and m_2 , the lengths to center of mass of links l_{c1} and l_{c2} and are the moments of inertia of links I_1 and I_2 .

2 Equations of motion

The state of the system is determined by θ_1 and θ_2 , angles of the first and second joints, respectively, and the angular velocities $\dot{\theta}_1$ and $\dot{\theta}_2$. The system dynamical equations are:

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Technical report created May 4, 2025; revised November 17, 2025.

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$$\ddot{\theta}_1 = -d_1^{-1}(d_2\ddot{\theta}_2 + \phi_1)$$

$$\ddot{\theta}_2 = \left(m_2 l_{c2}^2 + I_2 - \frac{d_2^2}{d_1} \right)^{-1} \left(\tau + \frac{d_2}{d_1} \phi_1 - \phi_2 \right)$$

$$d_1 = m_1 l_{c1}^2 + m_2 (l_1^2 + l_{c2}^2 + 2l_1 l_{c2} \cos \theta_2) + I_1 + I_2$$

$$d_2 = m_2 (l_{c2}^2 + l_1 l_{c2} \cos \theta_2) + I_2$$

$$\phi_1 = -m_2 l_1 l_{c2} \dot{\theta}_2^2 \sin \theta_2 - 2m_2 l_1 l_{c2} \dot{\theta}_2 \dot{\theta}_1 \sin \theta_2 + (m_1 l_{c1} + m_2 l_1) g \cos(\theta_1 - \pi/2) + \phi_2$$

$$\phi_2 = m_2 l_{c2} g \cos(\theta_1 + \theta_2 - \pi/2)$$

where m_1 and m_2 are the masses of links, l_1 and l_2 are the lengths of links, l_{c1} and l_{c2} are the lengths to center of mass of links, I_1 and I_2 are the moments of inertia of links, and τ is the torque applied at the second joint.

3 Coding in Python

The equations of motion can be easily coded in Python. We use a Python class to define the Acrobot object, as shown below. Probably the most used constants for simulations are the ones proposed by Sutton [4]. We define them as well as the gravitational acceleration by means of a Python dictionary. Note that we have implemented the `dynamics` as a static method.

```
import numpy as np

GRAVITATIONAL_ACCELERATION = 9.81

ACROBOT_SUTTON_PARAMS = {
    'm1': 1.0, 'l1': 1.0, 'lc1': 0.5, 'i1': 1.0,
    'm2': 1.0, 'l2': 1.0, 'lc2': 0.5, 'i2': 1.0,
    'g': GRAVITATIONAL_ACCELERATION
}

class Acrobot():

    def __init__(self, dt=0.05):
        self.state = np.array([0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0])
        self.params = ACROBOT_SUTTON_PARAMS
        self.dt = dt

    def reset(self):
        self.state = np.array([0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0])
        return self.state.copy()

    def step(self, torque):
        new_state = Acrobot.dynamics(self.state, torque, self.params)
        self.state = self.state + new_state * self.dt
        return self.state.copy()

    @staticmethod
    def dynamics(state, torque, params):
        theta1, theta2, theta1_dot, theta2_dot = state
        m1, l1, lc1, i1 = params['m1'], params['l1'], params['lc1'], params['i1']
```

```

m2, l2, lc2, i2 = params['m2'], params['l2'], params['lc2'], params['i2']
g = params['g']

s2 = np.sin(theta2)
c2 = np.cos(theta2)

phi2 = m2 * lc2 * g * np.cos(theta1 + theta2 - np.pi/2);
phi1 = - m2 * l1 * lc2 * theta2_dot**2 * s2 \
        - 2 * m2 * l1 * lc2 * theta2_dot * theta1_dot * s2 \
        + (m1 * lc1 + m2 * l1) * g * np.cos(theta1 - np.pi/2) + phi2;
d2 = m2 * (lc2**2 + l1 * lc2 * c2) + i2;
d1 = m1 * lc1**2 + m2 * (l1**2 + lc2**2 + 2 * l1 * lc2 * c2) + i1 + i2;

theta2_ddot = (torque + d2 / d1 * phi1 - phi2) / (m2 * lc2**2 + i2 - d2**2 / d1);
theta1_ddot = - (d2 * theta2_ddot + phi1) / d1;

return np.array([theta1_dot, theta2_dot, theta1_ddot, theta2_ddot])

```

An example of use is shown below. The default parameters are used for the acrobot. A torque $\tau = -1$ is applied for the first 50 steps. Then, the torque $\tau = +1$ is applied until the end of the simulation time. Finally, the `reset` method is called an example.

```

def main():
    a = Acrobot()
    current_time = 0.0
    for i in range(100):
        if i < 50:
            a.step(-1.0)
        else:
            a.step(+1.0)
        current_time += a.dt
    a.reset()

```

4 Concluding remarks

This report describes the equations of motion for the acrobot. From here we could keep studying the system behavior analyzing the stability with and without external forces, the controllability and the observability, or designing a controller such as an LQR by manipulating the system response through the control law.

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